

The Fat from the Seeds of *Vateria Indica*, Linn.

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When our work on this fat was ready for publication, a paper on the same subject appeared in the Journal of the Society of Chemical Industry (1931, 50, 471T) wherein Miss Jones had shown the fatty acids to consist of palmitic, stearic, arachidic and oleic acids. Since these results were not in accordance with our findings, we considered it desirable to recheck our data. The results that we have obtained appear to indicate the presence of myristic, stearic, lignoceric, elaidic (isooleic ?) and oleic acids in the total acids from the fat and a careful search for palmitic and arachidic acids did not reveal their presence. We have, as well, observed some other differences between our results and those published by Miss Jones and consequently consider it desirable to submit our data for publication.

Vateria indica, Linn (N. O. *Dipterocarpaceæ*; Vern. *Safed damar*) "is a large handsome tree forming evergreen forests at the foot of the Western Ghats from Kanara to Travancore. The tree yields a resin of considerable value known as 'piney resin' which in its properties compares very favourably with amber, and like copal is considerably employed in making varnishes" (Watt, "Dictionary of Economic Products," Vol. 6, Part IV, p. 223). The seed is ovoid 2—2½" long with a hard white kernel which on pressing or boiling is reported to yield 50 % of a pale yellow fat known as 'piney tallow.' In consistency the fat is midway between tallow and wax and has hitherto been employed for candle manufacture and for adulterating 'ghee.' The authors have recently suggested that the fat can be used as vegetable tallow (*Indian Forester*, 1932, 58, 69) ; and since it contains nearly 59% of stearic acid it can also serve as a convenient source of stearic acid.

The fat has been studied for its chemical and physical constants (Höhnel and Wolfbauer, *Pharm. Centralh.*, 1886, 26, 357 ; Crossley and Le Sueur, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1898, 17, 993 ; *Bull. Imp. Inst.*, 1930, 28, 280) but no systematic study appears to have been made of its chemical composition except that by Dal Sie (*Gazzetta*,

1896, 8, 107) and Miss Jones (*loc. cit.*), the results of both being at variance with ours. According to Dal Sie, who arrived at his conclusions mainly by the melting points of the acids obtained by fractional precipitation of the barium salts of the mixed acids, the fat consists of glycerides of palmitic acid (75 %) and oleic acid (25%), whereas Miss Jones records the components of the fatty acids as palmitic (10%), stearic (39%), arachidic (3%) and oleic acid (48%). Our results on the other hand indicate that the fat consists mainly of the glycerides of stearic (59 %), elaidic (*isooleic* ?) and oleic acids (39%) (Höhnel and Wolfbauer, *loc. cit.*).

The *Vateria indica* seeds, used in this investigation, were obtained from Mangalore. The kernels, on separation from the shells, were dried, powdered and expressed at 50—60° in a hydraulic press, which gave 14% of the fat ; and a further 8% was obtained from the meal on extraction with light petroleum. The average yield was between 20—22% (Bolton, "Oils, Fats and Fatty Foods," 1928, p. 267 and *Bull. Imp. Inst., loc. cit.*) and never as high as 50% as reported in some of the earlier works (Watt, *loc. cit.*). For determination of the physical and chemical constants, the freshly expressed fat was employed. The pale yellow colour of the fat is bleached on standing and iodine value is lowered. In some of the samples that had been standing exposed to air for a few weeks, the iodine value fell from 40 to 20.

General Characteristics of the Fat.

Consistency	...	tallow like.
Colour	...	pale yellow when fresh, white on standing.
M. p.	...	40°
Sp. gr. at 20°	...	0·9120
Refractive index at 25°	...	1·4556
Saponification value	...	190·4
Iodine value (Hanus)	..	40·0
Acetyl value	...	2·45
Hehner value	...	97·6
Acid value	...	1·4
Unsaponifiable matter	...	0·8 per cent.

Composition of the Fatty Acids.

Preliminary examination of the mixed fatty acids indicated the presence of a large percentage of stearic acid, the major portion of which was consequently removed by repeated crystallisation with 95% alcohol instead of the 70% (Armstrong, Allen and Moore, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, **44**, 64T). The remaining acids were then separated into the solid and the liquid acids by the usual lead salt-alcohol method (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, **13**, 806). The presence of a large percentage of solid acids both saturated and unsaturated (Cocks, Christian and Harding, *Analyst*, 1931, **56**, 368) in the total acids made it difficult to effect complete separation by a single Twitchell's procedure and therefore it had to be repeated thrice before a reasonably complete separation was possible. The solid and the liquid acids were then converted into their methyl esters and further separated into fractions by distillation under reduced pressure and the fractions singly examined. The results obtained in this manner are tabulated and discussed below.

Chemical Constants of the Mixed Fatty Acids.

Mean molecular weight	...	286
Iodine value	...	38.6
Saturated acids	...	61%
Unsaturated acids	...	39%

280 G. of the crude fatty acids were treated with a slight excess of sodium hydroxide and the resulting soap was incorporated with filter paper pulp. The mass was dried, powdered and extracted with ether in a Soxhlet and the extract examined for the unsaponifiable matter, as described later.

Saturated Acids.

237 G. of the mixed acids from which the unsaponifiable matter had been removed were crystallised several times from 95% alcohol and 70 g. of an acid (m. p. 68°-9° ; M. W. 283.3; Iodine value 0.5) was isolated. This was identified as stearic acid by its mixed melting point with an authentic sample.

The remaining 167 g. of the acids in the mother liquor were separated twice into solid and liquid acids by the Twitchell's

method. The following Table shows the state of separation of the different acids after the above two separations.

Method.	Acids.	Iodine value.	M. W.	Net weight.
Crystallisation	Stearic	0.5	283.3	70 g.
Twitchell's	(A) Solid (1st Twitchell)	3.6	280.0	63.5
	(B) Solid (2nd Twitchell)	18.6	280.0	5.5
	(C) Liquid	58.0	280.0	98.0

Solid Acids (A).—These were converted into their methyl esters and the unesterified acids removed by 5% sodium carbonate. 53.1 G. of the neutral esters were fractionated at 5-7 mm. pressure with the following results. The acids liberated from each of the fractions were fractionally crystallised for identification purposes.

Fractions.	B.p.	Weight.	M.W. of the acids.	Component of the esters.		
				Methyl myristate.	Methyl stearate.	Methyl lignocerate.
S ₁	125-180	4.15 g.	266.0	1.33 g.	2.82 g.	...
S ₂	180 - 85	6.50	275.0	1.06	5.44	...
S ₃	185 - 87	17.87	280.0	...	17.87	...
S ₄	187 - 90	12.40	282.0	...	12.40	...
S ₅	190 - 95	9.59	284.6	...	9.59	...
Residue	...	1.98	335.5	...	0.74	1.24 g.
Loss	...	0.61
Total	...	53.1	...	2.39	48.86	1.24

Fraction S₁.—Three crystallisations from acetone gave an acid (m.p. 68-69°; M. W. 283.2) which was identified as stearic acid by its mixed melting point with an authentic sample. The mother liquors on successive concentration and removal of the crystalline product gave a residue, m.p. 49-51° and M. W. 262.

Fraction S₂.—Two crystallisations from acetone yielded an acid which was identified as stearic acid. The mother liquor on succes-

sive concentration and removal of the crystalline product gave a residue, M. W. 262.5.

Fractions S₃, S₄ and S₅.—These fractions were identified as pure stearic acid, m.p. 68-69°; M. W. 284.5 and methyl ester, m.p. 38-39°.

The residue was a dark brown viscous mass, apparently consisting of a mixture of stearic and some higher solid acids along with their decomposition products. On crystallising thrice from 95% alcohol it yielded crystals, m.p. 77-78°, M.W. 368.6 with no change in the melting point on further crystallisation. Its mixed melting point with a sample of lignoceric acid from another source (Katti and Manjunath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 844) remained unchanged. Stearic acid was also isolated from the mother liquor and the residue being a complex, viscous and highly coloured mass was not identified further.

Palmitic acid, if at all it is present in the fatty acids, should have been found in the fractions S₁ and S₂ and in the solid acids (B) and (B₁) but no indication of its presence was found. The lower acid (m.p. 49-51°; M.W. 262), present in these fractions, on the other hand, appears to be myristic acid since its melting point is much lower than the melting point (55°) of the eutectic mixture of palmitic and stearic acids (Lewkowitsch "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes" 1921, Vol. I, p. 120).

Solid acids (B).—The mother liquor, from which the lead salts of the solid acids (A) had been separated, was concentrated to half its volume and then treated with the same volume of a hot alcoholic solution of lead acetate (20 g.) and the mixture allowed to stand overnight at 15-16°. The amount of precipitate thus obtained yielded 5.5 g. of solid acids (B) which on crystallisation from 95 % alcohol gave an acid m.p. 68-69° and M.W. 284.2. This was identified as stearic acid. Further quantity of stearic acid was obtained from the mother liquor by concentration. The residue, a brown viscous mass, had an iodine value 26 and M.W. 300. This appeared to contain oleic acid, which explains the high iodine value. The high molecular weight might possibly be due to the portion of the acids having got esterified during repeated crystallisations.

The above analyses lead us to conclude that the solid acids consist mainly of stearic acid with small amounts of myristic (not isolated) and lignoceric acid (isolated). Palmitic and arachidic acids as

reported by Miss Jones (*loc. cit.*) were not found. It is not clear from the brief data of her analysis whether she actually isolated and identified these acids or merely calculated their presence from the mean molecular weight of the fractions in which their presence was assumed. The latter procedure, it might be pointed out, is not perfect and in many cases leads to erroneous conclusions.

Unsaturated Acids

The liquid acids (C) were saponified to break up the esters which might have been formed in the alcohol treatment and the liberated acids when dissolved in ether, deposited a white solid (1.5 g.) which on crystallisation from 95% alcohol melted at 130° and had M. W. 316. This appears to be dihydroxystearic acid resulting from the atmospheric oxidation of the oleic acid or its isomers present in the liquid acids. The liquid acids, isolated from the ether solutions, had at this stage an iodine value of 57.6 and M. W. 280.

A portion of the acids on bromination (Lewkowitsch "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes" Vol. I, 6th edition, p. 585) gave no hexabromides, nor could any tetrabromide be isolated. Another portion was converted into its potassium soap and oxidised by a dilute potassium permanganate solution according to the method of Lapworth and Mottram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1628). The oxidised product was identified as dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 130-32°; M. W. 316) and the unoxidised portion (23%) was left as a viscous mass of mean M. W. 306.8 and the iodine value 7.8. A third portion of the acids was converted into potassium soap and oxidised by a concentrated solution of potassium permanganate according to the method of Bertram as modified by Hilditch and Priestman (*Analyst*, 1931, 56, 354; Smith and Chibnall, *Biolo. J.*, 1932, 26, 222). The unoxidised acids obtained after magnesium salt separation (10%) melted at 57-58° and had a M. W. of 288.

The above three experiments indicate that the unsaturated acids in the liquid portion (C) consist entirely of oleic acid or its isomers and that the acids of more than one double bond namely, linoleic, linolenic, etc., are absent. They also indicate that the liquid acids still contain some solid acids, portion of which is stearic acid as shown by Bertram's oxidation. The slightly higher molecular weight namely 288 is in all probability due to the incomplete destruction of the dihydroxystearic acid (Gay, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1932,

51, 126r). The balance of the substance, removed in Bertram's oxidation, appears to be of high molecular weight (M. W. 306·8, apparently dihydroxystearic acid) as shown by the oxidation method of Lapworth and Mottram (*loc cit.*).

Third Twitchell's separation.—64·25 G. of the de-esterified liquid acids were separated into solid and liquid acids and these were obtained in the following proportion.

Acids.	Wt.	Iodine value.	M. W.
Solid acids (B ₁)	11·9 g.	36·05	281
Liquid acids	52·35	63·90	288

The solid acids on crystallisation from 75% alcohol gave a product, m.p. 63-64° and M. W. 281·7. This was identified as stearic acid by its mixed melting point with a pure sample.

The liquid acids (52·35 g.), on standing, deposited a quantity of dihydroxystearic acid and even after removal of this the iodine value remained low (64). This indicated the presence of some saturated acids and consequently the liquid acids were submitted to Twitchell's method, once again.

Fourth Twitchell's separation.—The state of separation after this stage was as follows.

Acids.	Wt.	Iodine value.	M. W.
Solid acids	18·25 g.	80·4	282·7
Liquid acids	32·10	56·6	326·5
Dihydroxystearic acid	2·00	—	316·8

On twice crystallising from acetone, the solid acids yielded transparent plates, m.p. 43-44°, M.W. 284 and iodine value 85. This appeared to be elaidic acid (*isooleic acid* ?). The iodine value and the mean molecular weight of the liquid part indicated that it was still associated with some saturated substance.

The liquid acids were saponified by alcoholic potash to remove any ethyl esters and the resulting acids converted into methyl esters in the usual way. The esters on being dissolved in ether deposited a white solid, m. p. 63-64° (methyl ester of an isomeric dihydroxystearic acid). After removing this and the solvent ether, the 21·28 g. of the esters were fractionated at 3-5 mm. pressure with the following results:

Fractions.	B. p.	Weight.	Iodine value.	Component of the esters.	
				Methyl elaidate or oleate	Methyl ester of dihydroxy stearic acid.
L ₁	75-120	0.93 g.	10.2	—	—
L ₂	172-75	6.19	82.1	6.19 g.	—
L ₃	175-79	6.38	89.2	6.38	—
L ₄	179-85	2.12	74.4	1.84	0.28 g.
L ₅	185-240	2.26	35.7	0.94	1.32
Residue	—	2.90	38.0	1.28	1.62
Loss	—	0.50	—	—	—
Total	—	21.28	—	16.63	3.22

Fraction L₁ was too small for further investigation. It appeared to consist of some low boiling substance probably an ester of a saturated acid of low molecular weight and a little methyl oleate.

Fractions L₂ and L₃ appeared to be oleic acid. It cannot be said that the previous treatment was sufficient to completely remove the elaidic (*isooleic*?) from oleic acid hence it is not possible to say what fractions are exactly those of pure oleic acid.

Fraction L₄ was mostly methyl oleate. On standing it deposited a white crystalline substance, m. p. 67-68°, soluble in cold concentrated sulphuric acid and insoluble in alkali and only slightly soluble in petroleum ether. This appears to be the methyl ester of an isomeric dihydroxystearic acid. After removal of this, the iodine value of the fraction rose to 77. The fraction deposited again the same solid matter after standing for a couple of days. The above substance on saponification and liberation of the corresponding acid gave from acetone a crystalline product, m. p. 90-91°, M. W. 310. This appears to be dihydroxystearic acid, an oxidation product of elaidic acid. It might be pointed out here that the literature records the melting point of dihydroxystearic acid as 99-100° (Saytzeff, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1883, 33, 315) and also as 95.5° (Arnaud and Posternak, *Compt. rend.*, 1910, 150, 1130.)

Fraction L₅ was almost solid. It appeared to contain some methyl oleate.

The residue was a viscous dark mass which appeared to be a mixture of methyl oleate and the substance isolated in fractions L₄ and L₅ and some decomposed matter.

The above data on calculation gives the following percentage composition for the fatty acids :

Acids.	Wt.	%.
Myristic	2.76 g.	1.16
Stearic	139.25	58.76
Lignoceric	1.46	0.62
Elaidic (<i>isooleic</i> ?)	32.10	13.55
Oleic and elaidic (<i>isooleic</i> ?)	44.23	18.66
Dihydroxystearic (calculated as oleic acid)	8.43	3.55
Isomeric dihydroxystearic acid (calculated as oleic acid)	8.77	3.70
Total	237.00	100.00

Unaponifiable Matter.

From alcohol the unaponifiable matter deposited a curdy material, which after two crystallisations yielded a product melting at 75—77°. Under the microscope it appeared to consist partly of needle-like crystals and partly of a substance retained in the mother liquor. It gave no test for a sterol. In cold concentrated sulphuric acid it slowly developed a yellow colouration but the bulk remained insoluble. The amount of the substance being very small further identification was not possible.

The filtrate of this substance after standing overnight was found to deposit a granular substance which after three crystallisations yielded colourless plates, m. p., 133—34°. It gave all the characteristic colour tests of phytosterol and an acetate melting at 118-19°. The melting point of the substance and that of its acetate indicated its identity with sitosterol.

SUMMARY.

The fat from the seeds of *Vateria indica* has been found to contain the glycerides of myristic, stearic, lignoceric, elaidic (*isooleic*?) and oleic acids together with sitosterol melting at 133—34°. The presence of palmitic and arachidic acids has not been detected.

